

Impact of Climatic Change on the Population Dynamics of Desert Locust (*Schistocerca gregaria* forskal) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) and Management Practices in District Rajanpur Southern Punjab Pakistan

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Abstract

The desert locust (*Schistocerca gregaria*) has caused great losses to agriculture in Africa, the Middle East and South West Asia. Their annual migrations take them down wind where winter, spring and summer rains fall for breeding. The climate of Pakistan is changing year by year rainfall, soil moisture, soil and air temperatures, surface and boundaries winds effect the population of locust. The topography of District Rajanpur Southern Punjab and its tribal areas, Indus valley and Baluchistan are more suitable places for potential spring breeding. Seven control practices were tested against desert locust i.e. through beaver, defender micronair sprayer, plungery, power sprayers, tractor mounted jecto sprayer, shoulder mounted power sprayer and digging of trench. Beaver, helicopter, Defender micronair ULV sprayer proved to be excellent control in hopper, bands on grounds and adults immature pink colour flyer. The control practices were discussed in relation to climatic changes in desert locust population dynamics with reference to potential effects of different control practices, which shows that with the increase in temperature, humidity and rainfall the population of desert locust increases and vice versa. **Key Word:** *Schistocerca gregaria*; Desert locust; Locust control; Population dynamics; Locust control practices.

INTRODUCTION

Locust (*Schistocerca gregaria* forskal) invasion has been recognized as a major threat to agriculture and mankind since ancient times. When populations of these insects build up, certain species exhibit gregarious and migratory behavior, leading to the formation of spectacular swarms. Locusts were first recognized as a serious agricultural problem by British authorities in Iraq in the 1920s (Rooke, 1930). In countries such as Argentina, Australia, China, Niger and South Africa, populations of locusts and grasshoppers are monitored and treated as soon as outbreaks threaten. When pests cross national borders, internationally coordinated operations are necessary; Control failures and plague development have occurred with the desert locust in the Red Sea basin in 1986 and 1992 (Showler and Potter 1991) (Showler, 1995), with the migratory locust in Madagascar in 1995 (world bank 1998). Globally, about 64 countries representing 20% of land surface is subject to ravages of the desert locust during plague period. Rajanpur district Punjab Pakistan which is suitable breeding place because of more vegetation specially grasses with scattered trees and bushes. The soil type of district Rajanpur Punjab Pakistan is most suitable for breeding locust because structure of soil is porous and sandy that makes gullies and canal during rainy season in which moisture retain for long period where locust lay eggs easily. Breeding areas are thus, dictated by seasonal rains and the moment of swarms between these areas by prevailing winds, the resulting swarms then move south and west as these areas dry out, crop lands most at risk. (Meteorological data 2018,19,20) of Rajanpur District Punjab Pakistan in table 5. When plentiful rain falls and annual green vegetation develops, desert locust can increase rapidly in number and within a month or two, start to concentrate and become gregarious. Unless checked, this can lead to the formation of small groups or bands of wingless hoppers and small group or swarms of winged

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adults. There are some indications that, rainfall may increase as a result of increasing carbon dioxide levels leading to enhanced vegetation growth and moisture levels (Claussen et al. 2003). The desert locust exhibit two distinct behavioral phases the solitary phase when individual actively avoid one another and the gregarious phase when they form marching hopper bands and swarms (adult aggregation with high mobility). Both these stages of gregarious phase, hopper bands and swarms are capable of divesting crops and pastures (Uvarov 1966B, 1977B, Simpson 1999). Seasonal migration of the desert locust is influenced by the climatic factors such as temperature, wind and vegetation. Solitary locust fly at night for a few hours whereas the yellow gregarious swarms can fly for 12-15 hours in a day in warm weather and may settle just before or just after sun set depending on the availability of lush green vegetation on the ground. The height of the flying swarm is limited by the temperature and they fly between 1500 and 1800 meters above ground (Rainey, 1963 and Schaefer, 1976). A series of complex interaction between high rainfall, high survival rates, the lush green vegetation and the behavior wherein there is an increase in the rate at which hairs on the back legs are touched by other locusts in a group is responsible for change from the solitary to gregarious phase (Simpson et al. 2001). Changes from the solitary to the gregarious phase are the result of a complex interaction of factors including high rainfall allowing high survival rates, the type and distribution of the vegetation (Babah & Sword 2004). The desert locust only migrates to invasion areas in the form of swarm once they begun to Gregarise (Tratalos et al. 2010). Dense group that have strong cohesion among individual migrate long distance together are swarms and their size may range from less than one to 300 sq. miles. A sharp increase in the number of swarms over a period of months forms an upsurge, which can lead to plagues lasting several years, before population decline into periods of recession, when individuals are typically in the solitary phase (Bennett, 1975). Due to the reliance of locust on moistened soil for incubation and green vegetation for food in usually arid areas, some researchers have proposed that regional fluctuations in rainfall are the primary influence on locust numbers (Pedgley 1981 and Bennet 1975). However, theoretical studies by Cheke (1978), Blackith & Albrecht (1979) indicated that the population fluctuations of the desert locust may be due to endogenous dynamics. In constant, Farrow & Longstaff (1986) argued that migration tended to prevent the carrying capacity of the environment ever being exceeded and that endogenous models would therefore do little to explain locust population dynamics. More recently, Magor et al. (2007) proposed that a general reduction in locust activity since 1965 has occurred due to a change in rainfall patterns brought about by a more restricted north-south oscillation of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone. In Pakistan locust breeding season have also been demarcated main breeding seasons along with names of important areas as under. 1- Spring breeding (Feb to March) coastal area from west of Karachi to Baluchistan along with Iranian border, Southern Punjab Indus valley. 2- Summer breeding (July to October) normally occurs along with both sides of Indo-Pak border in the deserts of Tharparkar, Khipero and Cholistan. The Anti-Locust Research Centre, established in 1945, developed the use of chemical pesticides against locusts, selecting dieldrin as the most effective and economical control agent because of its long persistence (Bennett and Symmons 1972). Use of dieldrin allowed the treatment of barrier strips; migrating hopper bands would cross these strips and accumulate a lethal dose. The substitute organophosphate pesticides, such as fenitrothion and malathion, had shorter environmental persistence and were often repeatedly applied as blanket treatments over large areas. Ironically, such treatments may have caused greater environmental damage than the organochlorine treatments they were designed to replace (Rowley and Bennetto, 1993). Most modern control operations rely on safer organophosphates such as fenitrothion, carbamates such as bendiocarb, pyrethroids such as deltamethrin and lambda cyhalothrin, fipronil, and insect growth regulators such as dimilin and triflumeron (FAO, 1998). Environmental issues arising from the standard use of chemical pesticides against locusts and grasshoppers include the impact on operators, other people, livestock, birds, other terrestrial vertebrates (especially lizards), aquatic organisms (fish and invertebrates), and terrestrial arthropods, including the natural enemies of locusts and grasshoppers, as well as pollution issues, contamination of groundwater and wells, and disposal of surplus pesticide stocks (FAO, 1997). Martin et al (1998) investigated the impact of treating grassland with the pyrethroid deltamethrin to control grasshoppers on the availability of insects, primarily grasshoppers, as a food source for grassland songbirds.

Materials and Methods

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In the event of desert locust invasion, large scale chemical control still remains the only reliable methods to stop this plague, despite the many technical advances that have been made in recent years and the possibility of using some biological methods (mycopesticides) in the near future. Field observation and research carried out over several decades (in fact, throughout the 20th Century), have shown that upsurges and invasions of the desert locust are linked to favorable period of rainfall in reduced zones outbreak areas whose boundaries have been gradually identified. These outbreak areas must be constantly monitored and the first outbreak areas must be destroyed in priority by control measures over limited areas, before the cultivated zones are attacked and the invasion has a chance to spread Major, 1994. The control strategy has been applied with some degree of success since the 1960's and has been recommended since then by the FAO 1968, 1972, 1994a. 1994b. At that time, new methods of monitoring and control radically changed the basis of the problem in just a few years: new pesticides, new ULV application methods, efficient aerial spraying, barriers treatments, etc. They were highly instrumental in preventing major invasions, reducing the frequency of invasions and improving outbreak control (Lecoq, 2001 and Roy, 2001). In this combat operation, desert locust was control through aerial spray beaver, helicopter and on ground operation defender (micronair sprayer) vehicle mounted by using pesticide malathion ULV formulation. The water based sprayers are used in combat operation because these equipment's are available locally such as power sprayers, wheel barrow sprayers, tractor mounted jecto sprayer and vehicle mounted plungery sprayer. Lambdacyhalothrin 10EC were used for the control of locust. Ultra-low volume (ULV) spraying is now becoming the primary methods of application of both chemical and microbial pesticides ULV spraying has the advantage of allowing more exact control of the droplet spectrum. A technique using much smaller volumes of spray liquid, called ultra-low volume (ULV) spraying, was initially developed in the 1950s for use against the desert locust, and is now the most efficient and commonly used method. It is defined as applying between 0.5 – 5 liters of spray liquid per hectare, although between 0.5 and 1.0 liter per hectare is preferred for ULV locust control. This small quantity of concentrated insecticides is not mixed with water or any other liquid; the special formulation, known as a ULV (UL) formulation, is usually supplied ready to spray. In order to spread such small volumes over the target, the liquid must be broken up into small droplets light enough to be carried easily by the wind. To prevent these small droplets evaporating in the hot conditions that are typical during locust control operations, ULV formulation are based on oil rather than other solvents such as water or petrol fractions which may be not deposit (land on surface) very easily. They fall very slowly, so tend to be carried sideways by the wind rather than sedimenting on to horizontal surfaces. In addition, if they are too small or the wind is too light, they tend to go around objects rather than hit them, somewhat like smoke. However, if the droplets are the right size and there is sufficient wind, they deposit by impaction on vertical surface such as vegetation or locusts.

Special sprayers are required for ULV spraying if the insecticides is to be used safely and sufficiently. ULV sprayers can be carried by an operator (portable sprayer), mounted on a four wheel drive vehicle or on an aeroplane or helicopter (aircraft-mounted sprayer). In this combat operation desert locust infestations are sprayed with Ultra Low Volume (ULV) formulations of contact pesticides by using micro ULVA, micronair sprayers on ground. The ULV spray technique is designed to spray overlapping swaths of small droplets of a concentrated pesticides formulation on to locusts at very low dose rates. The pesticides can be directly sprayed on different molting stages like fledgling (fig no.1) with powers prayers if the infestations are small. Large infestations are sprayed with vehicle mounted sprayers like defender micronair sprayer, tractor mounted jecto sprayer, wheel barrow plungries and vehicle mounted plungries.

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Fig. No.1 Fledgling

Result and discussion

Desert locust control operations typically consist of a range of on the bases of availability of chemicals, equipment's and personals at remote locations. The window of opportunity for successful control may be as short as a few weeks from 1st report of infestation. Chemical control the main stay of current strategy, the insecticides used in different agriculture machinery for the control of locust were generally fast acting and knock down effect. Two groups of insecticides malathion and lambdacyhalothrin were used in the campaign for combating desert locust in Tehsil Rojhan District Rajanpur South Punjab.

- 1- Organophosphates: include the two most widely used locust insecticides, fenitrothion and malathion (Rowley and Bennetto 1993). They are moderately fast acting 2-8 hours, relatively non- persistent, but non-selective compounds. Malathion has the advantage of very low mammalian toxicity (WHO class iii, slightly hazardous).
- 2- Synthetic pyrethroids: examples are deltamethrin and lambdacyhalothrin, which are fast acting knock down effect within minutes varying levels of persistence and broad-spectrum. They are of fairly low mammalian toxicity Martin et al (1998).

The ultra-low volume (ULV) spray of malathion was used in beaver, helicopter and four wheel vehicle mounted defender micronair sprayer. The combat operation area are the natural habitat of migrant birds come from Siberia region of Russia to Pakistan are the insect's feeder and gorge themselves on large number of desert locust. The use of malathion rather than fenitrothion would greatly reduce risk to birds. The water based insecticide lambdacyhalothrin 10 EC was used in hand sprayer, tractor mounted jecto sprayer, wheel barrow plungries and vehicle mounted plungries.

The following management practices were used to control the desert locust population:

1-Beaver

ULV spraying through beaver used depending on desert locust life stages like hoppers, bands, adults immature flyers pink colour and on the swarms (fig no.2). Use beaver when infestation of swarm and surface area is highly infested with hopper bands more than hundred hectares, it gave good result for the control of hopper bands and settled swarm. Spraying on swarm by ground or air must take place in the relatively short window between down and departure of the swarm. Flying swarm spraying techniques is also gave excellent result but most desert locust spray aircrafts are not specially equipped to prevent entry of locust into air intake and deposit in front of beaver engine fans which may cause accidental encounters with the desert locusts. It is potentially the most rapid and pesticides efficient spray strategy (Symmons, 1993) ULV spraying is good technique for the control of desert locust, but it must be carried out under the right conditions and using properly calibrated ULV spraying equipment i.e., appropriate drop size was 60-80 micron, consume more than 80% volume of insecticide, emission height forward speed, track spacing and flow rate. Care must be taken that low volumes were deposited fairly uniformly over the target area.

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Fig. No.2 Control through Beaver

2-Helicopter

Like beaver helicopter by fitting two atomizer having droplet size 60-80 micron has been used for the campaign of combat operation against desert locust (fig no.3). ULV spraying techniques through helicopter was used on all the stages of life cycle of desert locust. The control through helicopter was first time used in combat operation against locust in Pakistan. It also gave good results on hoppers, hopper bands and on adult immature pink colour flyer. Band spraying on individual hopper bands by air and block spraying gave good results for the control of desert locust. Barrier spraying, settled swarm spraying, flying swarm spraying with insecticide malathion give good result for control of desert locust.

Fig. No. 3 Control through Helicopter

3-Defender micronair sprayer

Four wheel vehicle mounted micronair sprayer ULV called defender was most effective control on desert locust hoppers, bands on ground, small bushes and small trees also (fig no.4). One atomizer is fitted in defender and size of droplet size was 60-80 micron. One liter of insecticide of malathion is required for one hectare and dispersed rate was 833 ml/ minute. The defender used in campaign for the control of desert locust gave good result on the hoppers in bushes, bands on the ground, adults immature flyer pinkcolour and swarm. The disadvantage of ULV spraying defender is slightly increased hazard to untrained or ill-equipped operators handling concentrated formulation of insecticide malathion.

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Fig. No. 4 Control through Defender micronair sprayer

4- Plungery Sprayer

Two types of plungery sprayers were used in combat operation, one is wheel barrow plungery and other is vehicle mounted plungery 100 feet pipe is fitted with sprayer having the capacity of 100liter water tank (fig no.5). If the topography of soil is not suitable for the moment of sprayer and vehicle than these plungery sprayer was the best option, stand sprayer on one place and cover the area of 100 square feet around the sprayer. It gave good result on all types of soil topography like mountains, semi-mountains, gullies, scattered bushes and on the ground for the control of desert locust. The advantage of this sprayer is that if adults immature pink colour flyers and swarm sitting on the high tree canopy, the plungery pipe fastened with 25-30 feet high rod and sprayed easily on the canopy of trees for the control of desert locust. The disadvantage of this sprayer was that without water it did not work, so water bowser moves along with spraying areas.

Fig. No.5 Control through Plungery Sprayer

5-Shoulder mounted power sprayer.

Shoulder mounted powersprayer was used in combat operation having the capacity of 25liter water tank. Insecticide lambda cyhalothrin 10 EC was used 1 ml/1liter water for the control of hoppers in bushes and small bands on the ground (fig no.6). The disadvantage of this power sprayer is that the capacity of water tank is not so much to control the high population of desert locust. Hoppers, bands and adult immature pink colour flyers moved very fastly in different directions during the spray process. It only useful if locust population is very low and stage of locust is 2-3 instars. The disadvantage of use of shoulder mounted power sprayer is very laborious for human and creates health hazards for spray men.

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Fig. No.6 Control through Shoulder mounted power sprayer.

6-Tractor mounted jecto sprayer

Two type of tractor mounted jecto sprayer used in combat operation against desert locust, one jecto sprayer provided by PDMA (Provincial Disaster Management Authority) Punjab Pakistan, China made tractor mounted jecto sprayer having the capacity of 1000 liters water tank and other tractor mounted sprayer were the capacity of 400 liters water tank (fig no.7). Before starting the spray technicians and operators are advised to use the insecticide lambda cyhalothrin 10 EC 1 ml/liter of water to get effective control with minimizing pesticide use. The insecticide lambda cyhalothrin 10 EC used 1 ml/1 liter water gave good result against desert locust on bushes, hopper on trees, hopper bands and adults immature pink colour flyers and swarm sitting on ground bushes and small trees just after fledgling. The throw and mist of China made jecto gave excellent result on all the stages of life cycle of desert locust except swarms.

Fig. No. 6 Control through Tractor mounted Jecto sprayer

7-Digging Trench

Building barriers and digging trenches to control desert locust before they reach cultivated areas. 30 km long trench having 3 feet apart and 3 feet deep dug in front the marching bands of desert locust (fig no.8). This technique is useful when hopper bands mostly consist of 2-3 molting stages. When marching bands reached and trap in the trench, spray with plungeries and power sprayer with the dose of 1ml/1 liter water lambda cyhalothrin 10 EC gave good control on trap hopper bands. To determine the level of residues from locust control operations and effects on non-target fauna so, keeping in view the use of insecticide malathion ULV and lambda cyhalothrin 10 EC low dose @ 1ml/1 liter water have no side effect seen on life stock, birds and other fauna. However, during the 1986-89 plague, few monitoring or ecotoxicological monitoring studies were undertaken (Gruys, 1992). This made evaluation of circumstantial reports of non-target organisms impossible.

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Fig. No. 8 Control through Digging Trench

Table -1 Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature, Relative Humidity and Rainfall Data of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020.

Months	Max. Temp C°	Min. Temp C°	R.H (%)	Rainfall (mm)
Jan.	23.3	7.2	56.4	2.3
Feb.	25.1	9	55.7	3
Mar.	30.4	14.7	60	15
April	37.1	19.3	54.6	8.3
May	42.9	24.8	63.9	14
June	44.5	28.1	54.5	11.5
July	41.9	28.5	66.8	19.5
Aug.	41.6	28.4	56.7	20
Sep.	39.6	26.1	54.6	0
Oct.	33.1	23.1	53	11
Nov.	30.0	12.9	53	5
Dec.	28.9	9.3	51.7	4

Table-2 Summary of Average mean Meteorological Data of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020

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Year	2018				2019				2020			
Months	Max.T emp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)	Max.T emp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)	Max.Te mp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)
Jan.	26.2	7.6	57	0	22.5	6.6	50.4	7	21.4	7.5	62	0
Feb.	24.8	8.5	51	3	23.7	9.2	52.3	2	26.8	9.5	64	4
Mar.	34.31	16.2	56	0	29.8	12.7	60	8	27.1	15.4	64	37
Apr.	39.66	20.63	38.83	5	40.6	16.3	64	13	31.3	21	61	7
May.	40.38	25.55	60.87	0	45.6	24.2	67	28				
June.	44.46	28.09	45.02	17	44.6	28.3	64	6				
July.	40.21	27.83	63.67	24	43.7	29.3	70	15				
Aug.	39.98	28.61	45.58	5	43.4	28.3	68	35				
Sep.	38.23	26.92	47.33	0	41	25.4	62	0				
Oct.	31	24.7	46	0	35.3	21.5	60	22				
Nov.	28.6	11.9	46	0	31.5	13.9	60	10				
Dec.	28.6	9.9	42.4	2	29.2	8.8	61	6				

Year	2018				2019				2020			
Months	Max.T emp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)	Max.T emp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)	Max.Te mp C°	Min.Te mp C°	R.H %	Rainfall (mm)
Jan.	26.2	7.6	57	0	22.5	6.6	50.4	7	21.4	7.5	62	0
Feb.	24.8	8.5	51	3	23.7	9.2	52.3	2	26.8	9.5	64	4
Mar.	34.31	16.2	56	0	29.8	12.7	60	8	27.1	15.4	64	37
Apr.	39.66	20.63	38.83	5	40.6	16.3	64	13	31.3	21	61	7
May.	40.38	25.55	60.87	0	45.6	24.2	67	28				
June.	44.46	28.09	45.02	17	44.6	28.3	64	6				
July.	40.21	27.83	63.67	24	43.7	29.3	70	15				
Aug.	39.98	28.61	45.58	5	43.4	28.3	68	35				
Sep.	38.23	26.92	47.33	0	41	25.4	62	0				
Oct.	31	24.7	46	0	35.3	21.5	60	22				
Nov.	28.6	11.9	46	0	31.5	13.9	60	10				
Dec.	28.6	9.9	42.4	2	29.2	8.8	61	6				

Table 1 showed the maximum temperature data of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020, as temperature, directly affect the population of desert locust. That table shows when temperature becomes high the locust population increases. In the month of June, July and August when maximum temperature (44.5 C°, 41.9 C° and 41.6 C°) was observed, that increases the population of desert locust which will attack and move in swarm form in the next months of September and October. The population of desert locust also increases in the month of October, November and December when temperature was (33.1C°, 30.0C° and 28.9C°). The minimum temperature data of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020, as it effects the locust population. When the temperature becomes low it will increases the locust population. As in the month of October, November and December (23.1C°, 12.9C° and 9.3C°). The relative humidity of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020, as it directly effects the locust population. As the relative humidity increases it increases the population of desert locust. In the month of June, July and August when the relative humidity was (54.5, 66.8 and 56.7%), it increases the population of desert locust which will attack further in severe form. The rainfall data of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020, as the rainfall increases it increases the desert locust population. In the month of June, July and August when maximum rainfall (11.5, 19.5 and 20mm) was observed, that increases the population of desert locust. Table 2 showed the average mean of maximum temperature, minimum temperature, relative humidity and rainfall of District Rajanpur from January 2018 to April 2020. Seasonal migration of the desert locust is influenced by the climatic factors such as temperature, wind and vegetation. The soil type of district Rajanpur Punjab Pakistan is most suitable for breeding locust because structure of soil is porous and sandy that makes gullies and canal during rainy season in which moisture retain for long period where locust lay eggs easily in this area. The spring rainfall mainly in Rajanpur district Punjab Pakistan, the resulting swarms then move south and west as these areas dry out, crop lands most at risk. When plentiful rain falls and annual green vegetation develops, desert locust can increase rapidly in number and within a month or two, start to concentrate and become gregarious.

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